

➤ Preprints increase the visibility of your work!

7 million
abstract views

By February 2020 the preprint server bioRxiv had reached 7 million views/month.¹

3 million
PDF downloads

By March 2020 bioRxiv reached 3 million preprint downloads per month.¹

30,000
tweets per month

30,000 tweets per month mention and discuss preprints.²

40% more tweets
for bioRxiv preprints

Preprinting increases Twitter visibility for your manuscript and its reach with readers.³

37% feedback
from the community

37% of bioRxiv users received direct feedback via email.²

36% increase
in citations

Articles receive 36% more citations if they have a prior associated preprint.⁴

Infographics by ASAPbio Fellows:
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➤ **ASAPbio**

Find more information at ASAPbio.org

Sources:

1. bioRxiv API: <https://api.biorxiv.org/reports/usage>
2. Sever *et al.* bioRxiv 833400; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/833400>

3. Fraser *et al.* *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(2), 618–638
https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00043
4. Fu and Hughey. *eLife* 2019;8:e52646 doi: 10.7554/eLife.52646

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